

Strengthening character education planning based on Pancasila value in the international class program

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ABSTRACT

Education programs planned and implemented in schools have a great impact on the forming of the student's character and intelligence. This study aims to describe the planning of management to strengthen character education based on Pancasila values in the international class program at laboratory elementary school (Labschool) Universitas Negeri Malang (UM). Qualitative research with a case study research design is used in this study. The data was obtained through unstructured interviews with principals, teachers, education personnel, school committees, and stakeholder. All information is tested for credibility and validity through triangulation. The results of this study showed that planning activities in character education strengthening programs are divided into aspects of learning and non-learning. The formulation of the school's vision and mission is used as the basis for implementing character education in schools, by adjusting learning characteristics that refer to western education patterns, which are combined with eastern culture as outlined in student character-building activities. The impact of implementing school strategies in strengthening student character is inherent in students' daily lives, both in the environment where they live and in their school environment, and continues to carry over into adulthood.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education programs planned and implemented in schools have a great impact on the forming of student character and intelligence [1]–[3]. Programs both learning and non-learning received by students become an important need to build their future. Students as a young generation of Indonesians who can improve the dignity and identity of the nation are currently experiencing an alarming character crisis [4], [5]. Concern for others, tolerance, and other positive attitudes that are increasingly lost years become a concern in itself. To re-develop the character of the Indonesian nation that is increasingly eroded by the times, schools, educators, and the community is required to play a direct role in dealing with this problem [6]–[8].

Character education is necessary for basic education which is the entrance for a person to be able to continue the journey at the next level. This is supported by Samani and Hariyanto [9] which gives the meaning that character is a basic value that can build one's self because of the impact of cultural heritage, descendants, and environmental factors that can distinguish people from each other and implement attitudes

and daily behaviors. As a foundation, it must be built firmly to withstand the shocks, shocks, and currents of development and change of times. Planting the value of the Pancasila-based character into one of the characters that must be formed [10]. The value of national spirit is the way of thinking and acting and the breadth of students' insight on the importance of maintaining the dignity of the nation and country.

The implementation of the character education program itself has been regulated in presidential regulation (Perpres) number 87 of 2017 concerning strengthening character education (PPK) which state that the content of the implementation of PPK program implemented at the education unit level, namely strengthening tolerant values, honesty, religious, discipline, peace-loving, hard work, social care, creative, fond of reading, independent, national spirit, democratic, respect for achievement, curiosity, love of the country, communicative, responsibility, and caring for the environment [11]. Facing an era of increasingly massive globalization, the values of character education are deemed necessary by the government to be integrated with learning activities at the level of educational units or schools [10], [12], [13].

Theoretical and practical studies of various studies have been done concluded that the implementation of character education needs to be supported by good planning [1], [7], [14]. Without good planning, the character education strengthening program cannot be implemented properly in schools [15], [16]. This is related to the understanding aspects of the principal and teachers there are values contained in character education that can then be implemented into the school program [6], [17].

Previous research on character education has not done much to allude to the management aspect. Some previous research on character education is directed at the learning program and the results of the application of character education to the learning outcomes of students and changes in the character of students [18]–[20]. Other research emphasizes character education in the aspect of character-based learning development for students which are focused on the formation of students' leadership spirit [21]. While, Saidek, Islami, and Abdoludin [22] emphasize character education on the character formation of students in learning activities in the era of industry 4.0. Other research revealed that character education is directed toward teacher learning activities in the classroom where teachers are asked to be able to internalize character values in learning activities [23]–[25]. Therefore, this research is relatively new because there is not much mention of school planning to strengthen character education taken from the five basic values of Pancasila as a form of national character to be achieved through the main character education program in the implementation of the international class program.

One of the quality schools that are currently in great demand is the laboratory elementary school which is generally under the auspices of universities, one of which is the laboratory elementary school (Labschool) Universitas Negeri Malang (UM). This research seeks to analyze the planning of strengthening management of character education strengthening implemented in the international class program (ICP). The ICP program at elementary Labshool UM began in 2006 until now. This program uses a national curriculum (curriculum 2013) combined with the international curriculum, in this case, elementary Labshool UM under the auspices of UM Cambridge Centre Institute for developing laboratory education in collaboration with Cambridge Assessment International Education. Cambridge University is one of the top three universities in the world. This ICP program develops education by focusing on three fields of study, namely Mathematics, Science, and English. The implementation of the international class program goes hand in hand with the efforts to create a characteristic educational output.

Elementary Labshool UM, has a vision of the realization of an elementary school that excels in education to produce graduates who are pious, intellectual, characterful, cultured, and care about the environment in global life. Based on this vision, elementary Labshool UM has one mission of organizing and developing character and cultural education through full positive habituation to produce graduates of character. There are innovative programs for schools to strengthen children's character, following the five basic values of Pancasila as a form of national character to be achieved [10], [26]. In addition, there is also the development of educational and learning models that have been carried out by elementary Labshool UM, such as accelerated education models, mastery learning through per-unit modules, and individual learning services. In addition to this educational model, there are also innovative school programs to strengthen student's character, following the five basic values of Pancasila as a manifestation of the nation's character to be achieved, namely religious values, nationalism, cooperation, independence, and integrity, through programs character education such as literacy, femininity, presenting folk songs, honesty canteen, clean Friday (a community service program to clean the school environment), the “lost and found box” program, and many other innovative school programs.

Based on the exposure, research on school management to strengthen character education taken from the five basic values of Pancasila as a form of national character to be achieved through character education programs in the international class program at elementary Labshool UM, is very interesting to do. This study aims to describe management planning to strengthen character education based on the value of Pancasila in the international class program at elementary Labshool UM.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The formation of students' personalities through moral education, and manners education which can be interpreted the same as character-based education, aims to create students who become individuals who can socialize well [16], [27]. Individuals with character are needed to create a safe and conducive state of life, in which the individual has internal values that are influenced by certain social values, these values are also influenced by the culture attached to a country and more specifically in a country. certain areas [3], [10]. In the context of Indonesia, the essence of character education is value education, where education is based on noble values originating from the Indonesian nation, which the founders of the nation manifested based on the state called "Pancasila".

The importance of character education has been agreed upon by many experts. However, there are still differences in the methods, approaches, and methods of education [28], [29]. Some literature states that the traditional approach of inculcating certain values in students is still considered effective. However, other literature also mentions several approaches that can be used, including the cognitive moral development approach, value analysis approach, and value clarification approach, where these approaches are widely developed in western countries [30]–[32].

The application of character education needs to be supported by good school planning. This is related to how the implementation of character education programs can be carried out properly. The implementation of character education programs needs to be supported by the school management to regulate what planning, coordination, implementation, and supervision of character education programs in schools [33], [34]. The existence of school management in the form of character education strengthening management programs, helping principals and teachers to condition supporting aspects of the implementation of character education itself such as facilities, infrastructure, learning resources, and patterns of character building of students through extracurricular activities [35]–[37]. Therefore, character education in its implementation in schools needs to have the support of character education strengthening management. In its implementation sometimes both the principal and the teacher have difficulty understanding the purpose of the character education program itself and how to integrate it into learning activities [38]–[40]. Moreover, the values contained in the character education strengthening program must be integrated into management and learning activities in schools [41], [42]. So, it takes a strengthening process to be able to integrate values in character education that have been well-planned since the beginning.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research aims to describe management planning to strengthen character education in international class programs at elementary Labshool UM. This research started from the lack of research that mentions the school planning in order to strengthen character education taken from the five basic values of Pancasila as a form of national character to be achieved through character education programs, and the uniqueness of laboratory schools that were founded with the aim of being a pilot school and the development of school management and innovative educational practices integrated into the development of the university as a superior and leading institution. This is considered interesting by researchers, assuming that laboratory schools in universities implement innovative practices in order to plan for strengthening character education.

This research was approached qualitatively using a case study design. Researchers focused in depth on planning to strengthen character education based on values of nationalism, religiosity, integrity, independence, and cooperation. Data collection was carried out through in-depth unstructured interviews with informants. The key informants in this study were the principal, while additional informants were teachers, education personnel, school committees, and stakeholder. In addition, non-participant observation data collection techniques, and document review related to the problem under study, were also used by researchers. The collection of research data was conducted for five months (April-September 2020).

The findings were then verified through forum group discussion (FGD). Further analysis of the findings was also conducted through various discussions with lecturers and colleagues at the Universitas Negeri Malang, Indonesia who have expertise in the field of schooling and character education. The verification results of these findings are then explored academically using a review of previous research. All information comes from FGD involving the principal, 16 teachers, five education personnel, and eight school committees. In this study, data credibility checking was conducted using triangulation techniques to a key informant, namely the principal, and supporting informants, namely teachers, education personnel, and school committees. Two other techniques used in checking the credibility of this research data are random member checks and discussions with fellow researchers. Once the collection and analysis of data on the site are completed, it is carried out to check the consistency between conclusion formulation, provisional findings, data exposure, and field records. The data analysis technique was carried out as recommended [43], namely data reduction, data presentation, and inference/verification.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Results

Planning in the concept of management is the initial stage of the preparation of a program that will be carried out in an institution or organization. The planning process of strengthening character education programs in terms of structuring facilities and infrastructure as well as fostering student activities is prepared by the principal by involving teachers, education personnel, and also school committees as community representatives. The arrangement of school facilities and infrastructure and the development of students emphasized the five-character values that must be possessed by students, namely religion, nationalism, mutual cooperation, independence, and integrity. These five values in the activities of coaching students are carried out in learning and non-learning activities. In the learning activities, the values of these characters are integrated into the lesson plan compiled by the teacher. The implementation of character education in Labschool refers to the formulation of the school's vision and mission, which is adapted to the western education pattern, which of course is also combined with the eastern education pattern, which is contained in school programs related to character building. While non-learning programs are carried out on extracurricular coaching and also commemorations of religious holidays or national days.

The western education pattern in question is the application of the Cambridge curriculum adopted from Cambridge International Examinations (CIE). Planning plays an important role in making it easier for teachers to carry out their duties. Cambridge-based learning planning at Blitar city elementary Labshool UM analyzes the framework that has been determined by Cambridge University itself. Cambridge Framework, the syllabus of each subject, lesson plan, and teaching materials are materials prepared by the teacher before the learning process. The framework itself is a reference for daily learning. As in the making of the syllabus. In making the syllabus a teacher must also look at the framework first. Then the framework will be mapped according to the level and subjects. There is for students and teachers, i.e., so-called teacher resources. Learning planning process in the International Class Program, integrating between the national curriculum, Cambridge curriculum, and guidelines commitment making officer (PPK).

Planning the arrangement of facilities and infrastructure in accordance with the values of religious character, nationalism, mutual cooperation, independence, and integrity is organized by paying attention to the needs of students and the placement process through a forum of meetings or deliberations organized by the principal along with teachers and also education personnel. The planning process is carried out among others: i) Planning is made jointly; ii) The meeting preparation of school budget activity plans (RKAS); iii) To include the budget for character education in the RKAS; iv) The fulfillment of facilities and infrastructure; v) planning is carried out by deliberation, vi) The school seeks to provide facilities and infrastructure that support the activities of strengthening character education even though it is not yet perfect 100%. Then the facilities and infrastructure are arranged in a way that is easily accessible to students.

Planning the development of student activities is described in learning and non-learning activities both through intracurricular and extracurricular with habituation strategies. Learning programs in order to foster students in character strengthening programs include: i) The implementation of congregational dhuhr prayer, habituation of praying before and after activities in school, the study of religious activities, Friday charity; ii) Respect the flag and singing the national anthem of “*Indonesia Raya*” every morning and carry out the flag ceremony; iii) Conduct a clean-up Friday, train students to do class pickets, group work and discussions; iv) Train students to do tasks independently; and v) Provide learning programs that show the attitude of responsibility and can complete on time without coercion. While other activities that are not learned in the classroom include: i) Praying before and after doing activities; ii) Participating in independence day commemoration competitions, following ceremonial activities carried out by local governments such as “*Blitar Tempo Dulu*”; iii) Doing devotional work activities and help at home; iv) The existence of toilet training for the lower classes, students practicing are responsible for their own belongings in lockers that have been provided by the school; v) Awareness of students in cleaning their own places to eat after finishing their meals. Where in the coaching activities the teachers were given their respective duties by the headmaster to accompany the students in an effort to familiarize the values of these characters in their daily activities.

4.2. Discussion

Planning activities in character education strengthening programs based on nationalism values, religious, mutual cooperation, integrity and independence has been divided into two aspects, namely non-learning and learning aspects. The overall form of the planning program was formed in order to strengthen the character of students based on Pancasila values, good and detailed planning can facilitate the school in achieving the expected goals in the future [37], [44]. Planning is related to a series of activities that will be carried out in order to achieve goals in the future. Planning is a process of rational and systematic activities in setting all decisions, activities, or measures that will be implemented in the future in order to achieve

effective and efficient goals [45], [46]. In planning, there are always stages to achieve effective and efficient goals in an educational institution. These stages include the management process ranging from planning to evaluation.

The planning of the program to strengthen the character education of students in the International Class Program at Elementary Labshool UM, Blitar city, is outlined in the school activity plan and budget (RKAS). The formulation of school program planning is oriented to the school's vision and mission and adapted to the needs of students. Character education at the Labshool is also carried out by adjusting the characteristics of school learning that refers to the western education pattern by emphasizing the use of English as a school advantage combined with the eastern culture which is described in the student character building program. The effectiveness of school planning should result in a flexible and student-centered program, which includes learning programs, human resources, curricular development, student activities, school finance, curriculum elaboration into teaching materials for school buildings, laboratories, libraries, and school relationships with the community [44], [47].

The planning of the program to strengthen the character education of students at Elementary Labshool UM, Blitar city was carried out through a working meeting. The working meeting conducted by the school involves various components of the school, ranging from the principal, education personnel, teachers, school committees, parents, experts, and stakeholders, with the principal as the highest decision maker. The meeting was conducted through a mechanism of deliberation, conducted before the new school year. This is done in order to achieve the agreed objectives. The involvement of these parties is certainly very important to support the success of the character education strengthening program based on the integrity value of the Elementary Labshool UM, Blitar city [22], [48]. Therefore, planning is said to be effective if the headmaster involves school residents to work together in an effort to effectively program the school through collective efforts with the school community to achieve the goals set [31], [49]. The establishment of a school culture based on character education can be done through examples, spontaneous activities, routine activities, and conditioning of the school environment [50], [51]. Routine school activities are activities carried out by students continuously and consistently at all times [20], [52], [53]. Some previous research results show that one of the indicators of successful character formation based on nationalism values, religious, integrity, mutual cooperation, and independence is that students have behaviors that show those values inherently, meaning that the character is shown in daily behavior in society [54]–[56]. Efforts to strengthen the character of students must be formulated through appropriate strategies by the school so that the possibility of successful achievement of goals can be optimized [37], [57], [58].

Pancasila as a way of life provides direction and a foundation for the development of the nation's character. The function of Pancasila as a way of life means that Pancasila is also the soul and at the same time the personality of the nation. This means that the moral and character of the Indonesian nation is Pancasila [1], [10]. Only a nation that has a strong character can exist in the midst of an increasingly massive globalization era. The implementation of good and sustainable education is needed in an effort to realize the character of the nation [14], [28]. Therefore, it is important for education actors to be able to formulate appropriate plans in the context of strengthening character education so that they can be implemented and have a real impact on students.

5. CONCLUSION

The establishment of a laboratory school aims as a pilot school and the development of school management and innovative educational practices that are integrated into the development of the university as an excellent and leading institution. Laboratory schools in universities implement innovative practices in order to strengthen character education management based on nationalism values, religious, integrity, mutual cooperation, and independence. Planning activities in character education strengthening programs have been divided into two aspects, namely non-learning and learning aspects. The school's vision and mission become a reference in the preparation of character education programs at the Labshool, which adapt to the characteristics of western education patterns combined with eastern cultures that are described in student character-building programs. The impact of implementing school strategies in strengthening student character is inherent in students' daily lives, both in the environment where they live and in their school environment, and continues to carry over into adulthood. The results of this study are not free from several limitations, which are used as the basis for formulating recommendations for future research. The first limitation of this research is that this research is only conducted in one Labschool under the auspices of the university, considering a large number of Labschools in Indonesia, further research can be carried out in several Labschools in order to obtain more complete and interesting data. Second, this research is approached with a qualitative approach, future research can use a quantitative approach with a wider population, in order to describe what factors can influence the formation of student character based on Pancasila values.

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